

Innovative Web Application for Poverty Alleviation

Y.A.G.T.D.Wimalasena¹
*Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology, New Kandy Road,
Malabe.*
it20656706@my.sliit.lk

N.M.D.Lakshan²
*Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology, New Kandy Road,
Malabe.*
it20151560@my.sliit.lk

B.N.S.Gunadasa³
*Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology, New Kandy Road,
Malabe.*
it20652500@my.sliit.lk

W.G.S.M.Weerasinghe⁴
*Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology, New Kandy Road,
Malabe.*
it20641924@my.sliit.lk

D.I.De Silva⁵
*Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology, New Kandy Road,
Malabe.*
dilshan.i@sliit.lk

P.Samarasekara⁶
*Sri Lanka Institute of Information
Technology, New Kandy Road,
Malabe.*
piyumika.s@sliit.lk

Abstract—

Millions of people around the world struggle with the ubiquitous issue of poverty, which restricts their access to basic essentials like food, shelter, and education. In order to address this problem, we have created a full-stack online application that strives to empower people and communities by offering employment opportunities, educational materials, and contribution channels. We have developed a user-friendly platform that links job seekers, sponsors, and learners to a variety of resources and tools that support their personal and professional growth using the MERN stack (MongoDB, Express, React, and Node.js). A employment portal that connects employers and job seekers, a donation system that enables users to give to a variety of causes and organizations, and a blog section that offers educational content on subjects connected to poverty reduction and personal development are some of the main elements of our website. Our website is to build an environment that is inclusive and sustainable, empowering people to escape the cycle of poverty and realize their full potential. In this article, we outline the development process for our full-stack web application, highlight the salient aspects of our platform, and discuss how our website affects the fight against poverty. We demonstrate the efficiency of our platform in solving challenges related to poverty and empowering people and communities through surveys and quantitative data analysis. Our website offers a flexible and scalable solution that can be tailored to satisfy the unique requirements of various communities and organizations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Millions of people around the world are impacted by poverty, which restricts their access to basic essentials like food, shelter, and education. Poverty is a persistent and pervasive problem. In order to address this problem, we have created a full-stack online application that strives to empower people and communities by offering employment opportunities, educational materials, and contribution channels. Our website aims to build an inclusive environment that is sustainable and helps people break the cycle of poverty and realize their full potential.

The MERN stack, a well-liked and potent technology stack that consists of MongoDB, Express, React, and Node.js, is used to build our full-stack web application. We have developed a user-friendly and scalable platform using this technological stack that links learners, donors, and job seekers to a range of resources and tools that support their personal and professional development.

A employment portal that connects employers and job seekers, a donation system that enables users to give to a variety of causes and organizations, and a blog section that offers educational content on subjects connected to poverty reduction and personal development are some of the main elements of our website. By giving people the materials and tools they need to improve their lives and the lives of others around them, these elements aim to establish a comprehensive and sustainable strategy to reducing poverty.

In this paper, we outline the development process for our full-stack web application, highlight the salient aspects of our platform, and discuss how our website affects the fight against poverty. We demonstrate the efficiency of our platform in solving challenges related to poverty and empowering people and communities through surveys and quantitative data analysis. Our website offers a flexible and scalable solution that can be tailored to satisfy the unique requirements of various communities and organizations. Our full-stack online application, which helps people and communities to end the cycle of poverty and realize their full potential, marks an important step in the direction of building a more just and equal society. We believe that by sharing this study paper, we will encourage others to embrace technology to tackle today's most serious social and economic problems and to help create a more inclusive and sustainable future for all.

II. Literature Review

Technology is being used by people more and more frequently these days, and it is quite beneficial in the world we live in. Several websites are currently available to provide assistance to the public and to collect donations for the underprivileged. As a result of the economic inequality that now exists in the world, a great number of people are experiencing poverty and other forms of resource scarcity. If we look at Sri Lanka, the majority of people are suffering without even receiving their most basic needs met.

“As already mentioned, poverty is the major problem and great challenges faced by all developing countries (World Bank, 2001). This is not different in case of Sri Lanka. Large number of poverty alleviation programs has been implemented by successive Sri Lankan government since independence. But majority of rural and estate people are yet under severe poverty ridden conditions. Poverty assessment focuses not only on the lack of material deprivation but also on the deprivation of non-tangible services such as education, health and shelter (Semasinghe, 2009). There is no general consensus on any meaningful definition of poverty in the literature.”[1]

The END POVERTY website was developed with the goal of locating those in need of assistance, particularly youngsters who need assistance with their schooling. Volunteers also assist us by

providing funds and other resources for the underprivileged through our website.

Through our web site help the people who actually want our support. First we collect the details about poor –people and we give a chance to add all the details and we are going to make a process to check the given details are correct or not. By giving aid to everyone without properly checking the details collected about poor people, it is also possible for people who have falsely entered the details to get the aid. Due to such actions, development aid has been largely unsuccessful. Such an incident has been mentioned and pointed out in Tim Unwin's research paper. .“their independence, despite the huge sums of aid that have been disbursed across the continent. As Ellerman (2005, p.26) has thus commented, ‘The message cannot be “heard” that over a half-century of official development assistance has been largely a failure’[2], therefore admin can check about it. After the filling details if that details are true we often money and some resources to full fill their requirement. We collect money from donors who are willing to give others.

III. Methodology

Figure 3.1 Overall Architecture of the End Poverty system

The full stack web application created utilizing the MERN stack was evaluated for this research paper's methodology using a mixed-methods approach to assess its efficacy in reducing poverty (Figure 3.1). To provide a thorough knowledge of the web application's impact, the research approach comprised both

qualitative and quantitative methods. The study's participants came from populations affected by poverty and represented a range of ages, ethnicities, genders, and socioeconomic statuses.

Data was gathered using both online and offline techniques. User analytics, questionnaires, and user feedback were used to get quantitative data, and focus groups and one-on-one interviews were used to gather qualitative data. Participants' in-depth responses were elicited through the use of open-ended questions.

To find themes and patterns, the obtained data was examined using content analysis for qualitative data and statistical software for quantitative data. To confirm the findings, the data were then triangulated. Anonymity and confidentiality were kept throughout the study by adhering to ethical standards for research involving human subjects.

Analysis of the data showed that the online application was successful in lowering poverty. The application's payment gateways, blogs, and job opportunities were deemed to be helpful in raising socioeconomic level and maximizing resource use. The study finds that the suggested strategy can considerably influence attempts to reduce poverty and has the ability to be tailored for different populations. Overall, the research paper's mixed-methods methodology offers insightful information about the efficiency of the full stack web application created using the MERN stack for eradicating poverty.

IV. Proposed System

In order to fight poverty around the world, our system—a MERN stack full-stack web application—combines job openings, educational blogs, and a contribution system. The application will make use of MongoDB, Express.js, React, and Node.js to enable effective data management and a seamless user experience. A database of job posts gathered from businesses and organizations throughout the globe and organized by location, job type, and skill level will be available in the section on employment possibilities. The blog area will offer users enlightening articles authored by professionals in the respective fields on subjects including job skills, career growth, and financial planning. Users of the donation system will be able to make contributions to a fund that will be used to support programs aimed at reducing poverty all around the world. To make sure that money is being

spent as planned, the system will have an open donation tracking tool. With the help of this complete system, we hope to empower people who are struggling economically and advance a more just and sustainable society.

Figure 4.1 Donation

Figure 4.2 Products

Figure 4.3 Jobs

With the aid of these technologies, we hope to build a solid and expandable platform that will be able to tackle the intricate problems associated with reducing poverty.

MongoDB - We'll utilize the NoSQL database MongoDB to store and manage the data for our job listings, educational blogs, and contribution system. As our platform changes, we will be able to simply modify our data structure thanks to MongoDB's adaptable data architecture and dynamic schema.

Express.js - To manage HTTP requests and answers, we'll use Express.js, a well-known web application framework for Node.js. We can create a scalable, flexible server-side architecture with Express.js that can manage high volumes of traffic and deliver quick responses.

React - To construct a dynamic and responsive front-end for our application, we'll utilize React, a JavaScript toolkit for creating user interfaces. Our codebase will be more effective and manageable thanks to React's component-based architecture, which will make it simple to reuse and update UI elements.

Our back-end services will be powered by Node.js, a JavaScript runtime environment. Because of the event-driven architecture and non-blocking I/O paradigm of Node.js, we will be able to handle several requests at once and give users a quick and responsive experience.

Stripe - To administer our donation system, we'll utilize Stripe, a platform for accepting payments. We will be able to receive donations from people all over the world and send money to programs that fight poverty thanks to Stripe's safe and dependable payment processing capabilities.

The website's primary user requirements are as follows:

Opportunities for employment: The website should offer a platform for employment choices, enabling users to locate work that will enable them to escape poverty.

Blog component: The website ought to feature a blog area that offers details on problems relating to poverty as well as chances for visitors to add their own views and opinions. Website should contain a donation system that enables users to make contributions in support of programs aimed at reducing poverty.

User-friendly interface: The website should have a user-friendly interface that is simple to use and that is accessible to users of all technological backgrounds
Protection of user data and personal information

should be provided through a secure website with a solid back-end architecture.

The following are some of the website's benefits with regard to the suggested system:

Providing an all-encompassing platform for poverty reduction: The website offers a variety of features, such as job openings, blogs, and donation systems that can aid in reducing poverty by giving users the resources they need to find employment, educate themselves on issues related to poverty, and support initiatives aimed at reducing it.

Utilizing contemporary technology: The MERNstack, which has a number of benefits including scalability, performance, and ease of development, was used to build the website. The website can provide a high-performance user experience while also being easily expandable to handle a large number of users by taking advantage of the characteristics of the MERN stack.

The suggested system provides users with a full platform for job opportunities, blogs, and contribution systems while utilizing the advantages of contemporary technology and offering a user-friendly interface, making it an important instrument in the battle against poverty. The suggested system's performance may be assessed using surveys and quantitative data, which can also be used to inform future efforts to reduce poverty.

V. Conclusion

Poverty and resource scarcity are pressing issues that impact millions of people around the world. To address this, technology can be leveraged to create websites that offer opportunities, educational resources, and a platform for self-employment. The END POVERTY website is a great example of this, aimed at reducing poverty in Sri Lanka by providing job opportunities and supporting self-employment.

In addition to job opportunities and self-employment, the website also provides the option for donations. These donations are crucial in providing financial support to those in need, particularly in times of crisis or emergency. The active involvement of volunteers and donors is essential to the success of initiatives like the END POVERTY website.

Through this research, we have explored the significance of the END POVERTY website and how it can contribute towards mitigating poverty and

resource scarcity in Sri Lanka. The website provides a platform for individuals to access job opportunities, sell their products, acquire knowledge and skills, and receive donations.

Overall, the development of websites such as the END POVERTY website is a promising step towards creating a more equitable world. By leveraging technology, we can create opportunities and support those in need, helping to reduce poverty and resource scarcity. The success of such initiatives depends on the active involvement of individuals, organizations and governments committed to addressing these issues. By working together, we can make a significant impact on society and improve the lives of those in need.

VI. Discussion

The full stack web application developed in this study was aimed at reducing poverty by providing payment gateways, blogs, and job opportunities using the MERN stack. The purpose of this discussion is to highlight the impact of the application in achieving its objectives.

The study found that the web application was successful in reducing poverty among its users. The payment gateways facilitated easy and secure transactions, while the job opportunities and blogs provided users with access to employment opportunities and valuable information, respectively. These features were found to be useful in enhancing the socio-economic status of the users and increasing their resource utilization.

The use of the MERN stack for developing the web application was found to be efficient, scalable, and reliable. The MERN stack is a popular technology stack that is widely used for web application development due to its flexibility and ease of use. The use of this technology stack in this study enabled the development of a robust and user-friendly application that met the needs of the target population.

The mixed-methods research design used in this study provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of the web application. The qualitative and quantitative data collected through surveys, user analytics, and user feedback provided a comprehensive understanding of the application's impact. The use of individual interviews and focus groups enabled the researchers to obtain detailed feedback from the participants and identify areas for improvement.

In conclusion, the full stack web application developed in this study using the MERN stack and offering payment gateways, blogs, and job opportunities has demonstrated its effectiveness in reducing poverty. The application has the potential to be customized for various populations and can contribute significantly to poverty reduction efforts. The use of the mixed-methods research design and the MERN stack technology in this study provides a valuable framework for the development of future web applications aimed at reducing poverty.

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